

UNCERTAINTY OF A CRITICAL POINT ON THE FREEZING CURVE**Beycan İbrahimoğlu***Anadolu Plasma Technology Centre, Ankara-Turkey***Abstract**

P. W. Bridgman developed a method to measure the force acting on a moving piston of known area and conducted experiments on gases, liquids and solids at high pressures. He reported that there is no critical point on the freezing curve in his experiments on various materials. Researchers working in universities and laboratories in the USA, France, England, Germany, Russia, the Netherlands and other universities and laboratories have reported that there is no critical point on the melting curve at high pressures in their experiments on gases, liquids and solids with this method developed by P. W. Bridgman.

The main method of research in physical chemistry is experience. The new physical chemistry is an experimental science. A real physicochemical experiment is of great importance in the study of physical laws and processes. The method and methodology applied in determining the hypothesis put forward is the most important factor. Experiments are key to propose a hypothesis and solve a problem. Although the existence of a critical point on the melting curve seems theoretically and graphically possible, P. W. Bridgman and other researchers have reported that there is no critical point.

In our opinion, it is not possible to determine the existence of a critical point on the freezing curve by the method applied by P. W. Bridgman and other researchers in their experiments. With this method it was possible to determine the pressure and temperature dependent melting curve. For nearly a century, the presence or absence of a critical point on the freezing curve has been a matter of debate.

In the experiments conducted by P. W. Bridgman and other researchers, it was found that there was no critical point, but it is possible to determine the existence of a critical point by the experimental results of the intermittent metastable state on the freezing curve at high pressures or by applying the geometric method depending on the thermodynamic parameters of the substance.

Keywords: benzene, intermittent metastable state, graphical method, computer calculations, freezing curve, critical pressure.

Introduction

Phase transitions are one of the most interesting phenomena in physical chemistry. They differ by their nature and the Ehrenfest criteria are commonly used to classify them. The first type of phase transitions with an intermittent metastable state when pressure is applied can be called structural phase transitions. Changes in important physical properties of crystalline, electronic, dielectric-metal, dielectric-semiconductor and other materials during phase transitions occur at high pressure and contribute to the understanding of the physicochemical nature of matter. And recently, they were even able to obtain a boron-doped superconducting diamond. This will contribute greatly to the development of future electronics. On the other hand, the application of pressure gives rise to the practical possibility of synthesizing new materials with specific properties. The fundamental problem of high pressure physics is the study of the T-P diagram of a substance and the establishment of its crystal structure under certain T/P conditions.

High-pressure applications cover the automobile, aerospace, semiconductor and pharmaceutical industries, food and other sectors in physical, chemical and technical matters. The role of high pressure in achieving unique physical and chemical properties of materials in advanced high-tech industries and in basic and applied research is indisputable. The experimental setup developed for the study of solids, liquids and gases at high pressures and the experimental setup and experimental techniques used on the freezing curve are

examined by summarizing the work of P.W. Bridgman and other researchers [1] on the freezing curve.

Experimental setup and experimental technique

Although P. W. Bridgman and other researchers have developed some constructive modifications on a device that allows the creation of very high pressure, in general, the measurement methods are the same and the results are close to each other. For example: in the Keyes laboratory of Massachusetts Institute of Technology, fifty measuring instruments with a free piston pressure system have been in wide use for more than twenty years [1,3-11]. In conclusion, P.W. Bridgman divided his own work into two parts. First, by increasing the measurement technique to 12,000 kg/cm² and second, by increasing the pressure field to 50,000 bar/cm². Performed by the moving piston method, which makes it possible to determine all the necessary parameters. The general nature of the results is that the melting curve increases continuously with temperature and pressure, in combination no parameter changes, there is no reason to expect anything other than infinite growth of the melting curve. In experiments by Beatty and Bridgman, it was reported that there was no critical point [12]. The absolute values of the volumes of liquids and solids decrease along the melting line and the effect of pressure prevails over the effect of temperature. They also reported that the two most important results of measurements on more than 50 liquids are the reversal of the sign of $(d^2V/dT^2)_p$ with increasing temperature at a constant pressure of several thousand

kg/cm² and that $(dP/dT)_v$ is not only a function of volume [9,13,14].

Based on experiments conducted by P.W. Bridgman, Simon et al. [2] reported that the melting curve probably ends at a critical point. Rayet and Bridgman explicitly argue on liquid-solid equilibrium for argon up to 10,000 kg/cm² that the critical point cannot be ignored in any way. Several papers on this subject have come out of myBridgman laboratory. Later, new data on the melting curves of nitrogen and argon up to 5000 kg/cm² reported unlimited growth in the melting curve [3]. There are studies by Leiden and Kizom [4-8] in which the melting of certain stationary gases is determined over a much smaller pressure range than in Simon, but with greater accuracy. The Simon and Glatzel equation turned out to be applicable and its constants were determined. They reported that the Tait equation has wide applicability for volumes of liquids as a function of pressure:

$$V = V_0 - C \log [(B+P) / B]$$

Figure 0. Isotherms in the density-pressure (ρ - p) phase diagram and the intersection point of their extensions

Metastable state

From a physical point of view, matter is in a state of thermodynamic equilibrium. Metastability, then, is the non-equilibrium state of matter. Phase transitions in the equilibrium curves of evaporation, freezing and sublimation end in metastable states. Overall, the study of phase transitions under high pressure is very interesting and important for our future. Especially in the production of new types of materials.

The most commonly considered phase transitions are those with a change in temperature and pressure, under a constant pressure. Abrupt change in temperature and pressure at constant pressures is clearly visible on the melting curve with dashed metastable state. It has been reported that the metastable state determines the presence of a critical point on the liquid-solid equilibrium curve, just as it determines the presence of a critical point on the liquid-vapor equilibrium curve [16-21]. For this purpose, a special experimental setup was designed and experiments were carried out to obtain an intermittent metastable state at high pressures [22]. The abrupt temperature- and pressure-dependent change in the intermittent metastable state at constant pressures decreases with increasing pressure and becomes zero on the freezing curve. The point on the melting curve of benzene where the metastable state is reset at 2200atm pressure and 356K temperature is defined as the critical point of benzene [23-30].

According to Tammann and Moritz volume change the maximum pressure should return to zero at some final pressure:

$$\Delta v = a - b \log (C + \rho). \Delta v.$$

According to this equation, it should occur at 40,000 kg/cm² for CO [15].

In our studies, the CO₂ critical pressure of carbon dioxide was determined as 5700bar. Figure 0.

Although most of the studies devoted to melting at high pressure aim to solve the problem of the nature of the melting curve, the method applied in experiments has generally identified the existence of a critical point in the melting curve that depends on pressure and temperature. However, as determined above, many theoretical studies have reported that it is possible to have a critical point at high pressures. Experimentally applied at high pressures, the method has been the main subject of dispute whether the melting curve ends at the critical point, whether it has a maximum.

As mentioned above, this change in the properties of matter due to temperature and pressure is visible with a sudden jump. During a phase transition of the first type, the most important, primary comprehensive parameters change abruptly: specific volume (i.e. density), the amount of internal energy stored and the concentration of components. This change always occurs at a certain rate, which means that a limited amount of time is needed to "close" the entire gap in density or specific internal energy. During this time, the phase transition does not occur immediately in the entire volume of the substance, but gradually. In the first type of phase transitions, the abrupt jump and gradual transition occur stably at temperature and pressure values with the presence of a discontinuous metastable state.

Freezing of liquid benzene during cooling time at constant pressures, first in the discrete metastable state and then in the isothermic freezing process is completed. The point defining the system "freezes", pressure and temperature remain constant. The phase transformation completed by the first, second and super-type metastable state spontaneously formed under constant pressure by cooling benzene at 500atm pressure and 286.7K temperatures on the freezing curve is shown in Figure 1 and the I, II and III thermograms are given schematically.

The first thermogram (figure 1. I) shows the isothermic freezing time t of benzene cooled at point a between points d and c depending on the pressure and the completion of isothermic freezing at point c and the transition to solid phase along the d line. This thermogram is only the first type of phase transition resulting in a sustained metastable state.

The second thermogram (figure 1. II) shows that benzene cooled at point a supercools from freezing at point b to point c during t_1 , depending on the pressure. Suddenly rises from point c to point d during t_2 . Isothermic freezing between points d - e of temperature for time t_3 , terminating at point e and representing the solid phase along line f . This thermogram is the first type of

phase transition resulting in isothermic freezing after the intermittent metastable state.

Third (figure 1. III), thermogram Super phase transformation and super metastable state, although this phase transformation is still not realized in the defined experiments, it is graphically shown to be possible [31]. In the thermogram, benzene cooled at point a supercools between points b and c during t_1 , rises abruptly from point c to point d during t_2 and ends only in a metastable state without isothermic process. This phase transformation from the liquid phase to the solid phase with only metastable state characterizes the second type of phase transition.

Figure 1. Thermograms representing metastable states I, II and III.

The intermittent metastable state shown schematically on the freezing curve of liquid benzene at constant pressures of 500atm pressure and 286.7K temperature at constant pressures (Figure 1, II) is given in detail in Figure 2.

Figure 2. It was determined by experiments that the intermittent metastable state obtained on the freezing curve of liquid benzene is the sudden rise (adiabatic rise) of the liquid with supercooling under constant pressure $-\Delta T$, and Δp : isenthalpic pressure drop, which decreases with increasing pressure and becomes zero at 2200atm pressure and 356K temperature.

Figure 2. Freezing through metastable liquid formed by cooling the liquid-solid equilibrium graph of benzene, ab : isobaric cooling of stable liquid with temperature T_a , bc : isobaric supercooling of stable liquid with temperature T , $-\Delta T$: temperature drop during supercooling, cd : adiabatic and (isenthalpic) change of supercooled liquid with temperature T_c , $\Delta T = (-\Delta T)$: isenthalpic temperature rise, Δp : isenthalpic pressure drop, bcd : formation of metastable liquid, de : isothermic ($T = T_{be}$) and isobaric ($p = p_{bc} - \Delta p$) freezing, e : metastable solid, f : stable solid, $t_1 + t_2 + t_3 = t$: step times and total time to complete the batch metastable state

Computer results of the intermittent metastable state

The most promising way to create state diagrams is the optimal combination of experimental, theoretical and graphical methods followed by computer calculations. In this study, the experimentally obtained parameters of the intermittent metastable state are evaluated using the Tayt equation of state [45].

$$\rho = \frac{\rho_0}{1 - A \cdot \ln\left(\frac{B + P}{B + P_{\text{atm}}}\right)}$$

Where ρ_0 is the density at atmospheric pressure P_{atm} and temperature T , ρ is the density at some pressure P and temperature T .

P-T phase diagrams of benzene were drawn as a result of computer calculations considering intermittent metastable regions [45]. In addition, the diagrams are constructed by considering discrete metastable regions, and for benzene [53-55], the experimental and theoretical values of p-T in the subcritical region of the phase diagram do not exceed 1%. On the P-V diagram for a wide range of pressure variations in the high pressure region, the isotherm of the $T = 356$ K endpoint of the metastable state and the isotherm of the $T = 278.5$ K triple point of benzene are exactly very close at pressures in the range of 220 MPa and above. In this study, the experimental presence of the endpoint of the discontinuous metastable state at $P = 220$ MPa and temperature $T = 356$ K indicates the transformation of a liquid into a solid around this point.

The phase transition takes place in stages, from a disordered phase (liquid) to a less ordered phase and so to the most ordered phase (solid). That is, the transition develops through a series of intermittent metastable state-enhancing phases.

The experimental results determined with the discrete metastable state on the freezing curve of benzene at high pressure were found to coincide with the computer drawings and the confirmation equation.

Graphical method in geometry.

The main research topic of geometric thermodynamics, which is the basis of Gibbs' scientific papers, is

Figure 3. ρ - T , $p=\text{const}$ dependence of benzene.

the relationship between the physical and chemical properties of material bodies, their transformation into geometrically shaped images, their study and interpretation, which helps to precisely determine certain laws. The essence of geometric thermodynamics is not only to represent the state of thermodynamic systems using geometric images. These images are the subject of research, not the goal itself. Geometry establishes certain physical laws by applying methods. Geometry studies spatial relationships and shapes with graphics. Graphics is the only way to solve many technical problems. It is the only method of determining the physical and chemical properties of substances that have been reliably incorporated into the research methodology..

I. The dependence of $(dV/dT)p=\text{const}$ is based on the postulates that were later recognized as the postulates of the ideal gas law in determining the absolute temperature. The physical and theoretical importance of absolute temperature cannot be disputed.

II. The dependence of $(dp/dT)p=\text{const}$ bağılılığı, the point where the isobars meet on the (T) axis, indicated the ionization temperature for monatomic gases and the dissociation temperature for polyatomic gases [34-46]. This rule does not apply to Hydrogen gas [47-52].

It is also possible to apply the graphical method to liquid and solid phases of matter.

III. The dependence of $(d\rho/dT)p=\text{const}$ bağılılığı, applied to benzene in the liquid phase, determined the point at which the sublimation curve of the isobars ends. Figure 3. In addition, since experimental studies on the sublimation equilibrium curve involve technical requirements, it is important to graphically determine the point where the sublimation equilibrium curve ends. Applied to the test results of liquid benzene at $T=298$ K and $T=498$ K (ρ - T), $p=\text{constant}$ dependence, 168K temperature where the solid \rightleftharpoons vapor equilibrium curve ends and $\rho_k=1200$ kg/m³ critical density point were evaluated. The pressure of the critical density was determined as $P_s = (P_{\text{uç}}/T_{\text{uç}}) \times T_s = 0.023\text{bar}$.

IV. The dependence of $(d\rho/dP)T=\text{const}$ is applied to the liquid phase of benzene and the isotherms converge at one point at high pressure [24-31]. The parameters obtained by applying the graphical method to benzene and other substances are given in table 1.

Table1.

Critical temperature, critical pressure, critical density and sublimation curve endpoint values obtained graphically for various substances.

Matter	Chemical Name of Matter	Critical temperature K	Critical density kg/m^3	Critical pressure MPa	desubduction curve ends temperature, K
M-Toloudin	C7H9N	436	1085	200	178
O- Toloudin	C7H9N	303.15	1115	140	153
Benzen	C6H6	562.7	1200	220	160
Benzonitril	C7H5N	700	1150	185	198
N-Dekan	C10H22	617.6	839	130	140
O-Ksilen	C8H10	630	990	205	120
N-hepten	C6H17	540	885	425	80

The pressure-temperature phase diagram of benzene was drawn using the values given in table 1 obtained by experimental and graphical methods. The p-T phase diagram of benzene is given in figure 4.

Figure 4.

In the liquid phase of benzene, the isotherms converge at a pressure of 2200atm, which is a critical point on the melting curve. The point determined by experimental, computer and graphical methods at 2200atm

pressure represents the critical point on the freezing curve of benzene. The critical point determined by the dashed metastable state on the freezing curve of benzene at high pressure is drawn in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Temperature and time diagram of the critical point on the freezing curve of benzene

According to the theory of L. D. Landau [12], during phase transitions of the first kind, the distribution function over the energy or density of the system has two **bimodal** maxima. At the first-order phase transition point, the density distribution is indeed bimodal. In this case, the greater the number of particles in the system, the higher and narrower the peaks on the bimodal curve. The highest maximum corresponds to the most favorable, stable state of the system and the second maximum corresponds to a less favorable, metastable state. At the transition point, the heights of the maxima become the same and the system can coexist in both states at the same time. This is illustrated in the temperature versus time diagram on the freezing curve of benzene. Figure 5.

Conclusion

At high pressures and temperatures, it is very difficult to determine the intermittent metastable burst of melting by experiments. Although the existence of a critical point on the melting curve is theoretically possible, it cannot be determined experimentally by measuring the volume with the force acting on the moving piston whose area is known.

In experiments, the absolute values of the volumes of liquids and solids decrease along the melting line and the effect of pressure dominates the effect of temperature. The compressibility of the solid phase at the melting point is never greater than the compressibility of the liquid phase at the melting point, usually less than 25% and not much more.

These approaches and a phase transition of the first kind imply the existence of metastable states for each of the phases: evaporation, melting and sublimation.

By obtaining a discrete metastable state on the liquid-solid equilibrium curve of benzene, the existence of a base point at a pressure of 2200atm and a temperature of 356K was determined by computer investigations and graphical method and this point was defined as the critical pressure.

Our metastable and graphic research highlights the following issues.

1. The first type of phase transitions, achieved by continuous or discontinuous metastable state, are completed by an isothermic process.
2. The second type of phase transformation is the "super metastable phase transformation", which represents the transformation from a metastable state to a solid phase without an isothermic process, plotted graphically.
3. Critical temperature at the point on the liquid-vapor equilibrium curve where the metastable state ends under constant pressure with increasing temperature T_{cr} ,
4. The point pressure at which the metastable state ends under constant pressure by cooling the liquid-solid equilibrium curve p_{cr} ,
5. The point at which the metastable state ends under constant pressure by cooling the solid-vapor equilibrium curve is represented by the critical density ρ_{cr}

6. With the transition of the liquid phase to the solid phase, the density of the substance between the liquid and solid phases is equalized $\rho_L = \rho_S$

7. The evaporation equilibrium curve is a function of temperature, the freezing curve is a function of pressure, the sublimation equilibrium curve is a function of density.

References

1. P. W. Bridgman, Rev. of. Modern Physics 18, № 1, 1 (1946)
2. F. Simon, M. Ruheman n and W. A. M. Edwards, Zschr. f. phys. Chem, B 6, 331 (1930). Кривые плавления водорода, неона, азота и аргона.
3. O. K. Rice, J. Chem. Phys. 6, 472 (1938). Equilibrium solid-liquid for argon.
4. W. H. Keesom a. K. Cluisis, Proc. Amst. Acad. Sci. 34, 605 (1931). Переход жидкого гелия I в жидкий гелий II под давлением.
5. W. H. Keesom a. J. H. C. Lisman, Kon. Akad. van Wetens. Amst.Proc. 34, 598 (1931). Кривая плавления водорода до 450 кг/см².
6. W. H. Keesom a. J. H. C. Lisman, Kon. Akad. van Wetens. Amst.Proc. 35, 605 (1932). Кривая плавления-водорода до 610 кг/см².
7. W. H. Keesom a. J. H. C. Lisman, Kon. Akad. van Wetens. Amst.Proc. 36, 378 (1933). Кривая плавления неона до 200 кг/см².
8. J. H. C. Lismana. W. H. Keesom, Physica 2, 901 (1935). Кривая плавления кислорода до 170 кг/см².
9. P. W. Bridgman, J. Chem. Phys. 9, 794 (1941): a) Замерзание и сжатие до 50 000 kg/cm²; Proc. Am. Acad. Arts Sci. 74, 399 (1942): b) Параметры замерзания и сжатия 21 вещества до 50 000 кг/см²
10. Frederick G. Keyes, Ind. Eng. Chem. 23, 1375 (1931). Техника высоких давлений.
11. Frederick G. Keyes, Proc. Am. Acad. 68,505 (1933). Методика и тех. ника, применяемые при выполнении программы Массачузетского технологического института по исследованию P — V зависимости для воды до 460° С.
12. J. A. Beattie a. O. C. Bridgman, Ann. d. Physick 12, 827 (1932). Об измерениях с поршневым манометром. II. Влияние старения и вязкости масла на константу манометра; зависимость между истинным и эффективным диаметром поршня.
13. P. W. Bridgman, Proc. Am. Acad. Arts Sci. 66, 185 (1931). Объёмы восемнадцати жидкостей как функции давления и температуры.
14. P. W. Bridgman, J. Chem. Phys. 9, 794 (1941): a) Замерзание и сжатие до 50 000 kg/cm²; Proc. Am. Acad. Arts Sci. 74, 399 (1942): b) Параметры замерзания и сжатия 21 вещества до 50 000 кг/см²
15. O. Tamann u. G. Moritz, Zschr. f. anorg. allgem. Chemie 218, 60 (1934). О ходе кривых плавления.
16. V. G. Baidakov & S. P. Protsenko. Metastable phase equilibria in a Lennard-Jones system. *Journal of Engineering Thermophysics* volume 16, pages249–258 (2007).

17. V.G. Baidakov, Singular point of a system of Lennard-Jones particles at negative pressures. V.G. Baidakov, S.P. Protsenko, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 95(1) (2005), 015701–1–015701–4
18. V.G. Baidakov, Metastable extension of the sublimation curve and the critical contact point. V.G. Baidakov, S.P. Protsenko, *J. Chem. Phys.* 124(23), 231101–231103 (2006)
19. Gregg Jaeger. The Ehrenfest Classification of Phase Transitions: Introduction and Evolution. May 1998 Archive for History of Exact Sciences 53(1):51–81. DOI:10.1007/s004070050021
20. Landau L.D., Lifshitz E.M. *Statistical physics. Part 1.* M.: Nauka, 1976.
21. M. SKVORTSOV. USUAL AND UNUSUAL PHASE TRANSITIONS. *Soros educational journal* N 8, 1996. st.103-108. (<http://stat.phys.spbu.ru/Metod/Faz-perex2.pdf>)
22. B.I. Farzaliev, A.M. Ragimov. Investigation of phase transitions in liquids. BAKU 1984 Preprint №1 Institute of Physics of the Academy of Sciences of Azerbaijan.
23. M. Azreg-Ainou, A. Huseynov, B. Ibrahimoglu, Phase equilibrium and metastability of liquid benzene at high pressures, *J Chem Phys*, 124 (2006). <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.2198808>
24. M. Azreg-Ainou, B. Ibrahimoglu, High-pressure effects on the benzene pre-crystallization metastable states, *Eur. Phys. J. E*, 42 (2019) 1-10. <https://doi.org/10.1140/epje/i2019-11863-2>
25. V. D. ALEXANDROV, B. IBRAGIMOGLY, A. E. POKINTELITSA, PRESSURE FALLING EFFECTS ACCOMPANYING PHASE TRANSFORMATIONS OF BENZENE UNDER THE ACCESSION OF COMPREHENSIVE COMPRESSION UDC 541.64: 542.62: 546.23 *Modern Building Materials Edition 2015 1 (111) UKRAÏNA*
26. B. Ibrahimogly, Chidem Kanbesh, I.M. Ahmedov PHASE TRANSFORMATIONS OF BENZENE IN TERMS OF LOW TEMPERATURES AND HIGH PRESSURES 23, *Chemistry Problems* N4-2015, p 367-371 UDK-541.64; 546-13. Baku Azerbaijan
27. Beycan Ibrahimoglu, Deniz Uner, Ayfer Veziroglu, Fuat Karakaya, Beycan Ibrahimoglu. Construction of phase diagrams to estimate phase transitions at high pressures: A critical point at the solid liquid transition for benzene. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*. Volume 46, Issue 29, 26 April 2021, Pages 15168-15180
28. B. İbrahimoğlu, B İbrahimoğlu, T. Gasimiva, B.C. Askerli. A new type of phase diagram of pure substances. *News of the Azerbaijan national academy of elites. Physics-texnika and piyaziyat hands series, physics and astronomy 2022.* No 2. YDK 536 539. p.107-114
29. B. İbrahimoğlu, B İbrahimoğlu, T. Gasimiva, B.C. Askerli. A new type of phase diagram of pure substances. *News of the Azerbaijan national academy of elites. Physics-texnika and piyaziyat hands series, physics and astronomy 2022.* No 2. YDK 536 539. p.107-114
30. Beycan İBRAHIMOĞLU, Yüksel SARIKAYA and Beycan İBRAHIMOĞLUJR. Utilization of Graphical Method to Determine the Characteristics of Desublimation Equilibrium Curve of Benzonitrile. "International Journal of Modern Engineering Research (IJMER)", vol. 12(08), 2022, pp 01-07.
31. Beycan Ibrahimoglu, Fuat Karakaya, Tarana Gasimova, Beycan İBRAHIMOĞLU, Super phase transition and super metastable state, *Chemical Physics*, 2021ya). Contents lists available at ScienceDirect *Chemical Physics journal homepage: https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemphys.2021.11131*
32. J. H. Dymond & R. Malhotra. The Tait equation: 100 years on. *International Journal of Thermophysics* volume 9, pages 941–951 (1988)
33. Safarov, M.M. Khasanova, S.S. Gulomov, M.M. Radzhabova, D.Sh. Davlatov, R.Dzh. Khakimov, D.Sh. Rafiev, S.S. Radzhabov, A.R. Oymatova, Khushainov, Z.Kh. Analysis of applicability of Tate type equation to different classes of substances in a condensed state on the example of density. II. Density calculation *Vestnik Natsionalnogo Universiteta; ISSN 1993-6923; CLASSICAL AND QUANTUM MECHANICS, GENERAL PHYSICS (S71)*
34. B.I. Farzaliev., A.M. Ragimov, A.T. Hajiyev. Graphical definition of the parameters of the triple equilibrium point. UDC 533.77. "OIL AND GAS" 24. June 1985. Baku, Azerbaijan).
35. Farzaliev B. I, Aliev N. F On benzene phase transitions at high pressures // *Thermodynamic and transport properties. substances. Themed. Science. Work.* - Baku, AzPU, 1989. - pp.61-65.
36. Farzaliev B.I, Aliev N.F., Determination of gases by graphical analytic method. *Proceedings of a Scientific Conference Az TU, Baku, 1992.* P. 21 (Russian).
37. Ibrahimoglu B., Grafoanalytical of Critical Pressure in Gas. Finding with the method, vol. 17, 2. Ankara: *Journal of Turkish Journal of Science and Technology of Turk*; 1994.
38. Ibrahimoglu B.İ, Ataer O.E., Determination of a Node on the Melting Curve, ULIBTK-97, 11 th National Congress of Business Science and Technology, Edirne, 1997. P.33.
39. B. İbrahimoglu, Karakaya, F., Ibrahimoglu, B. (2021). Determination of the Real Critical Pressure and Critical Density of Substances. *Academia Letters*, Article 2704. <https://doi.org/10.20935/AL2704>.
40. Beycan Ibrahimoglu, B.A. Grigoryev, Berk Gökbek, Beycan Ibrahimoglu jun.. Phase transitions and the phase diagrams A case of benzene. *Научно-технический сборник · ВЕСТИ ГАЗОВОЙ НАУКИ.* № 4 (49) / 2021. UDC 543.272.75:544.344.015.4. st.140-152.
41. Beycan İbrahimoglu, Beycan İbrahimoglu Jr., Eda Bolayır. Phase Transitions and the Phase Diagrams. *SCIREA Journal of Chemistry* <http://www.scirea.org/journal/Chemistry>. November 1, 2021 Volume 6, Issue 2, April 2021.
42. Beycan İBRAHIMOĞLU, Yüksel SARIKAYA and Beycan İBRAHIMOĞLUJR. Utilization of Graphical Method to Determine the Characteristics of Desublimation

Equilibrium Curve of Benzonitrile. International OPEN ACCESS Journal Of Modern Engineering Research (IJMER). | IJMER | ISSN: 2249–6645 | www.ijmer.com | Vol. 12 | Iss. 8 | August 2022 | 1 |.

43. Beycan İbrahimoglu, Yuksel Sarikaya, Beycan Jr. Ibrahimoglu. Critical Parameters of Pure Substances. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-1861011/v1>. August 3rd, 2022. This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.

44. Beycan İbrahimoglu, Çiğdem Kanbeş Dindar, Hazal Erol, Salih Karasarı, DETERMINATION OF 1/V-T (P, CONSTANT) DIAGRAMS OF HYDROGEN GASES BY GRAPH-ANALYTICAL METHODS, Journal of Thermal Engineering, Vol. 3, No. 1, pp. 1071-1077, January, 2017, Manuscript Received 29 December.

45. Beycan İbrahimoglu, Beycan İbrahimojlu(jn) Critical States at Phase Transitions of Pure Substances. ISBN 978-3-031-09965-6 Springer Nature Tiergartenstr. 15-17, 69121 Heidelberg, Germany.

46. B. A. Grigoryev, Beycan Ibrahimoglu, Faruk Comert Beycan Ibrahimoglu jun. Determination of the real critical density of substances. Научно-технический сборник · ВЕСТИ ГАЗОВОЙ НАУКИ. № 1 (46) / 2021. 46-51. Moskova.

47. B. Ibrahimoglu, T. Nejat Veziroglu, Aydin Huseynov. Study of thermodynamic parameters of hydrogen gas by grapho-analytic metho. International Journal of Hydrogen Energy 30 (2005) 515 – 519. doi:10.1016/j.ijhydene.2004.04.013

48. T. Veziroglu, B. Ibrahimoglu, A. Huseynov and D. Schur, et al., “Study of Thermodynamic Parameters of Hydrogen Gas by Grapho-Analytic Method,” Editor of a Chapter in Hydrogen Materials Science and Chemistry of Carbon Nanomaterials, 225-232. ©2004 Kluwer Academic Publishers, Netherlands.

49. B. İbrahimoglu, N. Veziroglu ve A. Huseynov, Schur, D., (2004), Study of thermodynamic parameters of hydrogen gas by grapho- analytic method. Hydrogen Materials Science and Chemistry of Carbon Nanomaterials, S. 225–232.

50. B. Ibrahimoglu, T. Veziroglu, A. Huseynov and D. Schur, “Study of Thermodynamic Parameters of Hydrogen Gas by Grapho-Analytic Method,” Hydrogen Materials Science and Chemistry of Carbon Nanomaterials, NATO Science Series II: Mathematics, Physics and Chemistry, 2005, Volume 172, 225–232.

51. Beycan Ibrahimoglu, Gozde Tekeli. Application of graphic and graphic-analytic geometry systems on the liquid and gas phases of matter. Научно-технический сборник · ВЕСТИ ГАЗОВОЙ НАУКИ. № 1 (38) / 2019. 163-170. Moskova.

52. B. Ibrahimoglu, Y. Sarikaya, A. Veziroglu, B. Ibrahimoglu Jr., M. Onal, B. Gokbel. Supercritical phases of hydrogen, International Journal of Hydrogen Energy, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2021.07.032>.

53. Igor Alexandrov, Boris Grigor'ev, A.A. Gerasimov, B.V. Nemzer. Thermophysical Properties of Individual Hydrocarbons of Petroleum and Natural Gases. Properties, Methods, and Low-Carbon Technologies. ISBN: 9780323952170. DOI:10.1016/C2021-0-02883-2 .

54. N. B. Vargaftik, Y. K. Vinogradov, V. S. Yargin. Handbook of Physical Properties of Liquids and Gases. ISBN Imprimir:978-1-56700-063-4. ISBN Online:978-1-56700-375-8

55. Bruce E. Poling, John M. Prausnitz, John P. O'Connell. Properties of Gases and Liquids, 5th Edition. ISBN: 9780070116825